

THE ROLE OF INTELLECTUAL GAMES IN ACTIVATING THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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Abstract: The main types of didactic games are intellectual (mental), action and mixed games. These games help the participants to develop mental, physical, moral, psychological, aesthetic, artistic entrepreneurship, work and other skills. In the process of education, didactic games are mainly used, which show students' motivations for learning and their inclination to a profession that increases their abilities and interests in various directions. In this article, the use of interactive methods of didactic games in the educational process methodical recommendations are given about its effectiveness.

Key words: Didactic games, computer tool, "Brain-ring", small groups, educational method, education, knowledge.

The concept of "Educational technology" to the concept of "Educational methodology". is relatively wide. Educational method — the collective tasks of the educational process solution-oriented method of joint activity of the teacher and students and the educational methodology is based on the science of teaching a specific subject represents a system of methods, rules and methods. Educational technology is a general process of achieving educational goals content, i.e. pre-planned educational process on the basis of a holistic system, step-by-step implementation, a specific method to achieve a specific goal, development of a system of methods and tools, their effective and efficient use and represents high-level management of the educational process.

The central problem of pedagogical technology is the identity of the student is to ensure the achievement of the educational goal through development. A teacher is a scientist VPBespalko recognized that the pedagogical system is the basis of pedagogical technology he states that it consists of the following elements: * u> 1) student; 2) the goal of education; 3) education - content of education; 4) educational process; 5) teacher or technical means; 6) organization of education forms. Therefore, it should be recognized that pedagogical technology is a science of the holistic process of educational activity. Especially interactive lesson to teach.

One of the interactive methods is the use of "Working in small groups" technology. The method of using this technology is as follows: - the direction of activity is determined. Interrelated issues are identified from the problem;

- the necessary basis is created. Readers should gain a greater understanding of the subject;
- groups are defined. Students are divided into groups of 7-8 people;
- a clear instruction is given. Independent work, crossword, test preparation;
- the starting student is appointed in advance. Independently, works on the subject or section, composes questions, crosswords, evaluates test answers;
- an expert or assistant (assistant) student is appointed, they help in conducting the game, evaluate and analyze the answers;
- captains are elected from the groups. The captain is a sober person, he will die for his team without violating the rules of the game;
- the process is supported and guided by the teacher. He monitors the game, and after the game is over, he announces the total score of the students. It is then discussed;
- the names of students divided into 3 groups are written on the blackboard, the maximum points according to the purpose of the lesson are indicated, each point collected according to the plan is written against the student's last name.
- As a result of the interaction between the teacher and the student, the student is known in addition to simply acquiring knowledge, i.e. learning

- Usually, the teacher chooses the method of teaching and teaching a foreign language. The content of the course remains largely unchanged, but the way it is delivered to the student may change.

- If the task is about giving an argument, methods such as presentations or interactive lectures are the most effective methods. The best way to discuss the problems is to divide the students into small groups and have a group discussion. Discussion, Brainstorming method can be used for this. It is known that didactic games such as plot, role-playing, creative, businessmen, conference, game exercises are important for students' independent wide and thorough knowledge acquisition, which are educational, strengthen knowledge, and repeat educational materials. , is significant in that it is expressed as knowledge control games. Students' creative thinking, independent knowledge acquisition.

The role of games is special. Activity game lesson - in the process of solving problems on the subject of the lesson an exercise in mastering new knowledge by ensuring the active participation of students.

Role-playing lesson - assigning pre-determined roles to students in learning the issues on the subject of the lesson and organizing them to fulfill this role during the lesson a lesson to strengthen knowledge based on achievement.

Theatrical lesson is a lesson that provides in-depth, clear information on the subject of the lesson by organizing scenes related to the topic of the lesson.

the subject of the lesson is uo yicna cnuqui, clearly ma lumouai ueiisn lesson.

A computer lesson is a lesson conducted on the basis of computer materials (multimedia, virtual training course, etc.)

An auction lesson is a lesson to demonstrate how much each student knows about a particular subject.

Fair lesson - pre-mastery of the subject of the lesson in pieces a lesson that is taught through an interesting explanation to the class based on student interaction lesson

A game lesson is a lesson to organize students' learning through a game appropriate to the subject of the lesson.

Court lesson - a lesson to organize a new topic by organizing a "court" process with the students, appropriate to the topic of the lesson.

A concert lesson is an exercise of presenting the subject of the lesson in the form of a concert, which provides an opportunity to activate students and strengthen their knowledge.

The lesson conducted by investigative experts is a proof and explanation exercise based on interesting question-answers and analysis with the help of students who have thoroughly studied the topic of the lesson in advance. they create comfort for their stay.

Integral (integrated) lesson is a lesson organized on topics that are convenient for integration of several subjects, which increases students' interest in various subjects and ensures their activity in the educational process. By teaching students about interdisciplinarity, such classes help them become more human. full understanding of the scientific foundations of the structure, formation of a scientific worldview serves to develop creative thinking.

Field of Miracles lessons are fun games with students to find the correct answers to various questions within a set time and encourage the winners to develop thinking, ingenuity and intelligence in students, expanding knowledge. forms the qualities of going.

Didactic game activities can be divided into game exercises with plots, role-playing games, creative games, business games, conferences, depending on the combination of students' learning and game activities. The teacher and pedagogue must first prepare students for individual (individual) and then group games and conduct them, and after the game is successful, prepare them for public games. Because in order for students to actively participate in didactic games, they should have the necessary knowledge, skills, and abilities, and cooperation and mutual support should be established among the group. Among the didactic game sessions,

conference sessions also occupy an important place. Conference sessions are important in activating students' cognitive activities, broadening the view of the scientific world, introducing additional and local materials, acquiring skills and qualifications for independent work with scientific and popular scientific literature, and conscious preparation for independent life. Before the conference training session, the goals and tasks of the training topic are determined, and additional scientific and popular literature on this topic is reviewed. A week before the training, the topic of the training is announced and literature is recommended for preparing for it. in introducing additional and local materials, independent work with scientific and popular literature is important in acquiring skills and qualifications, conscious preparation for independent life. Before the conference training session, the goals and tasks of the training topic are determined, and additional scientific and popular literature on this topic is reviewed. A week before the training, the topic of the training is announced and literature is recommended for preparing for it. in introducing additional and local materials, independent work with scientific and popular literature is important in acquiring skills and qualifications, conscious preparation for independent life. Before the conference training session, the goals and tasks of the training topic are determined, and additional scientific and popular literature on this topic is reviewed. A week before the training, the topic of the training is announced and literature is recommended for preparing for it. additional scientific, scientific-popular literature on this topic is reviewed. A week before the training, the topic of the training is announced and literature is recommended for preparing for it. additional scientific, scientific-popular literature on this topic is reviewed. A week before the training, the topic of the training is announced and literature is recommended for preparing for it.

The use of new pedagogical technology in the educational system does not require thinking based on a certain pattern, but arriving at a common solution through diverse creative research.

References:

1. A. Zununov, N. Hotamov, J. Esonov. Methodology of teaching literature at school. Tashkent, "Teacher" 1993.
2. Q. Yuldoshev. Scientific and theoretical foundations of teaching literature. Tashkent, "Teacher", 1996.
3. Q. Yoldoshev, O. Madaev, A. Abdurrazakov. Literature teaching methodology, software guide. Tashkent, 1994.